

This is an English translation of the initial version of the game developed within and for the German-speaking context. This context is known for the fact that socioeconomic disadvantage translates into educational inequality in schools to a much greater extent than in other countries. At the same time, some of the references relevant to the game—such as the contexts from which families migrate to German-speaking countries—reflect the countries of origin of the developers during the game’s creation. This may change over time, as may other aspects. As you play the game, we also invite you to familiarize yourself with the context—or, as we say in German, “the country and its people.”

Overview: Information about the game and its design

This game is based on Bourdieu's theories on how schools reproduce social inequalities. It is designed to help students of educational science to engage with social science issues and theories beyond the study of texts. The simulation game was collaboratively developed by Mathias Weibel, Sandra Thinnes (née Włodarczyk), Janes Heuer, and Tanja Sturm and has been tested several times at various colleges and universities. The current version is the result of several rounds of tests, revisions and constructive feedback from participants.

We have described the game’s development and purpose in an article that also gives a brief overview of the theoretical background and addresses some of the benefits of using theoretical simulation games like this one in higher education (Sturm, Weibel, Włodarczyk 2017). We recommend reading this article, but as of now it is only available in German via Inklusion Online (<https://www.inklusion-online.net/index.php/inklusion-online/article/view/402>).

After publication of the article, we received numerous requests asking us for the game. In keeping with the theme of social inequality, we decided to make the German version of the game available as a free download through Inklusion Online. We are grateful to the editors of Inklusion Online for hosting the game on the magazine's website. We are also grateful for the opportunity to make the English version of the game available through the ED-TED resource bank.

You will find the game instructions and game materials in this document. You can print out and cut out the documents. We recommend using a cutting machine and laminating the materials. Then you're ready to go!

Contents

The game consists of the following materials:

- **Game instructions;** print out at least one set of instructions per game
- **Character cards** with names and gender indicators (m or f); print out as many as you need
- **Lottery tickets** for determining class affiliation
- **Biographical context cards** sorted into **upper class (green)**, **middle class (red)**, **working class (yellow)**: parents' occupation, family situation, (no) immigrant background, living conditions, (no) special educational needs.

Print all of these out. It helps to use colored paper (green, red, yellow) to keep materials for the different class affiliations in order. All characteristics should stay sorted by class and put individually into labeled envelopes. The players randomly create their character

for the game by drawing different characteristics from the envelope of their assigned class.

- **Personal event cards**
- **General event cards**
- **Capital conversion sheet**

You will also need one die per game.

We welcome feedback and suggestions for further development of the game. We look forward to your comments and ideas. Please email us at:

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Have fun preparing and playing the game!

Tanja Sturm, Matthias Weibel and Sandra Thinnés

Reproducing social inequality through schools

Simulation game for discussing Pierre Bourdieu's theory of cultural reproduction (especially Bourdieu, 1974), developed by Mathias Weibel, Sandra Thinnés (née Włodarczyk), Tanja Sturm, and Janes Heuer (for further information in German, see Sturm, Weibel, & Włodarczyk, 2017)

Gameplay

One set of the game can be played by 4 to 8 players. One round of the game lasts about 60 minutes. Additionally, you should plan at least 30 minutes for introduction and reflection.

Structure and theoretical background of the game

The game is designed to encourage players to engage with Bourdieu's theories on cultural reproduction in schools with a particular focus on the reproduction of social inequality. The game is designed to simulate a fictional school career. Players use character cards to develop characters with different social and biographical experiences. According to Bourdieu (1992), individuals have unequal access to contested social goods due to the varying degrees of social, economic and cultural capital available to them. The game simulates how capital volume and its particular makeup changes for the characters over the course of their (fictional) school careers. During the game, players are required to use their capital and convert it strategically in order to increase it; otherwise, they lose it. Players can actively influence the conversion of capital on a personal level (through *personal event cards*), but the school as an organization that qualifies, selects, and legitimizes limits their freedom by setting various requirements and expectations (*general event cards*) for all 'students'. This includes control over students' degree of participation in educational processes and the awarding of certificates. According to Bourdieu, students differ in how their social and biographical experiences match the school's expectations (Bourdieu 1974). This reproduces social inequalities that the players experience over the course of the game.

Contents

You need the following materials for the game:

- **Game instructions**
- **Character cards** with names and gender indicators (m or f)
- **Lottery tickets for determining class affiliation**

- 4 players: 2 working class, 1 middle class, 1 upper class
- 5 players: 2 working class, 2 middle class, 1 upper class
- 6 players: 3 working class, 2 middle class, 1 upper class
- 7 players: 3 working class, 2 middle class, 2 upper class
- 8 players: 4 working class, 2 middle class, 2 upper class
- **Biographical context cards** sorted into **upper class (green)**, **middle class (red)**, **working class (yellow)**: parents' occupation, family situation, (no) immigrant background, living conditions, (no) special educational needs.
 There are different sheets for each class that affect the likelihood of drawing particular features. Print all of these out and make sure to keep them apart. It helps to use colored paper (green, red, yellow) to keep materials for the different classes in order. All characteristics should be placed individually in an envelope – one envelope per class. The players randomly create their character for the game by drawing different characteristics from the envelope of their assigned class.
- **Personal event cards**
- **General event cards**
- **Capital conversion sheets**
- **1 die**, not included

Gameplay

Setup

1. Creating your characters
 - Every player draws a character card. Class affiliation (**upper class (green)**, **middle class (red)**, **working class (yellow)**) is determined by drawing a lottery ticket.
 - Next, players draw their biographical context cards from the envelope of their assigned class. It's important to keep classes separate because class affiliation increases or decreases the chance of drawing favorable features with regard to economic, social and cultural capital.
 After drawing their context cards, each player should have a character card with one individual feature for each of the five dimensions (parents' occupation, family situation, (no) immigrant background, living conditions, (no) special educational needs).
 - To avoid drawing multiple features for the same dimension (e.g. two cards for parents' occupation) the cards can be sorted by dimension in the respective class envelopes. Alternatively, the course leader can prefill the character cards for the players.

2. Assigning capital
 Before the game begins, everyone receives their starting capital based on their class affiliation:

Upper class	Economic capital	350
	Social capital	150
	Cultural capital	150
Middle class	Economic capital	250

Social capital	110
Cultural capital	110

Working class

Economic capital	100
Social capital	60
Cultural capital	60

Additionally, players can lose or receive further capital based on their social background and personal circumstances as determined by the biographical context cards:

Family background	Single parent	Economic capital - 50
	Married / living together	Economic capital + 25
Living conditions	Homeowner	Economic capital + 50
Parents' occupation	Temporarily out of work	Economic capital - 15
	University educated	Cultural capital + 50
Immigrant background	Immigrant background	Cultural capital - 20
Special educational needs and disabilities (SEND)	Only for the following SEND: learning difficulties, speech and language, social and emotional needs	Cultural capital - 20
	For all SEND	Social capital - 10

3. Starting the game

Players can use and/or exchange their capital in each round of the game. The youngest player starts and draws a personal event card. Some cards require a capital conversion, while others offer an optional capital conversion. Optional conversion cards indicate at the bottom how long they are valid. As long as they are valid, players can decide whether to keep the card and convert again or return the card. There is no refund if the card is returned, but players don't need to spend additional capital either. In addition to the cards already in play, each player can draw one card per round. A player's turn ends when they have made their decision based on their personal event cards. After each player has had a turn, a general event card is drawn that affects all players.

Each round ends with the distribution of additional Capital based on class affiliation. Players must keep track of their capital using pen, paper and the capital conversion sheet.

Capital distribution after each round:

Upper class

Economic capital	40
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	Social capital	20
	Cultural capital	30
Middle class	Economic capital	25
	Social capital	10
	Cultural capital	10
Working class	Economic capital	15
	Social capital	5
	Cultural capital	5

After every third round of the game, the players finish a school level. In order to advance to the next level, players must have accumulated a specified amount of cultural capital points. This increases with each level.

Level 1:	80 Cultural capital points
Level 2:	110 Cultural capital points
Level 3:	250 Cultural capital points

4. End of the game

The game ends when the third school level has been completed. The aim of the game is to complete all school levels and to accumulate as much capital as possible. If a player cannot respond to general events or successfully complete a school level due to a lack of capital they are eliminated from the game. This encourages players to maximize their capital points. If several players are excluded before completing the third level, their capital is added up and compared with that of the others.

Notes on different types of capital

Economic capital:	Money or any form of material possession that can be directly converted into money, such as real estate, stocks, etc.
Social capital	The ability to take advantage of a network of relationships; resources based on group membership (e.g. family, political party, clubs, etc.)
Cultural capital	Is divided into three types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectified cultural capital: material cultural goods such as books, works of art, instruments, etc. • Incorporated cultural capital: internalized cultural skills and knowledge acquired through the investment of time spent on education • Institutionalized cultural capital: educational qualifications such as school leaving certificates, university degrees, etc.
Symbolic capital	Any kind of social recognition (e.g. the prestige that comes with educational titles); symbolic capital is part of Bourdieu's theories but not a part of this game

Suggestions for discussing the game

The game is intended to stimulate debate and reflection on Bourdieu's theories on social inequality and its (re)production through schools. Players are encouraged to discuss how they felt about their character throughout the game. The following questions can be used as prompts for discussion:

- What courses of action were/weren't open to you during the game?
- What helped/hindered you in achieving the goal of the game?
- What consequences did your starting position (class affiliation + biographical background) have for the game?
- How did your character's biographical background help/hinder you in converting capital?
- What changes to the game would be necessary if we wanted to give every player equal opportunity for achieving the goal of the game?

The game is based on Bourdieu's theory on the distribution of different types of capital and its effect on schools and society as a whole. In the game, this is experienced from the perspective of the characters created in the beginning. These characters are limited to a few relevant aspects (class affiliation and biographical attributes). This limitation carries the risk of stereotyping the characters and their experiences and may suggest the idea that the characters' background (class affiliation and biographical attributes) determines the characters' actions. The game with its formal rules reinforces this deterministic interpretation. This opens up further possibilities for discussion:

- To what extent is the game based on stereotypical characters? Does it offer an opportunity to reflect on different social milieus and how they shape people's experiences?
- To what extent does the game suggest that social differences have a deterministic effect on people's actions?

Sources

Bourdieu, P. (1974). The School as a Conservative Force: Scholastic and Cultural Inequalities. In J. Eggleston (Ed.), *Contemporary Research in the Sociology of Education* (pp. 32-46). London: Routledge.

Bourdieu, P. (1984). *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. London: Routledge.

Bourdieu, Pierre (1992). *Die verborgenen Mechanismen der Macht*. Schriften zu Politik & Kultur 1. Hamburg: VSA.

Bourdieu, P. (2001). *Wie die Kultur zum Bauern kommt. Über Bildung, Klassen und Erziehung*. Hamburg: VSA.

Sturm, T., Weibel, M., & Wlodarczyk, S. (2017). Simulationsspiel als hochschuldidaktisches Medium zur Auseinandersetzung mit soziologischen Theorien: – am Beispiel von Bourdieus ‚Reproduktion sozialer Ungleichheit durch die Schule‘. *Zeitschrift für Inklusion*. <https://www.inklusion-online.net/index.php/inklusion-online/article/view/402>

Matteo (male)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Samuel (male)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Luca (male)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Dario (male)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Paula (female)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Sara (female)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Jenny (female)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Elisa (female)

Class affiliation:	Parents' occupation:
Family background:	Immigrant background:
Living conditions:	Special educational needs:

Lottery tickets for class affiliation

Upper class	Upper class
Middle class	Middle class
Working class	Working class
Working class	Working class

Biographical context cards – Upper class

Parents' occupation: University professor	Parents' occupation: University professor	Parents' occupation: University professor
Parents' occupation: University professor	Parents' occupation: Doctor	Parents' occupation: Doctor
Parents' occupation: Doctor	Parents' occupation: Lawyer	Parents' occupation: Lawyer
Parents' occupation: Lawyer	Parents' occupation: Corporate executive	Parents' occupation: Corporate executive
Parents' occupation: Judge	Parents' occupation: Pilot	Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 50 employees

Biographical context cards – Upper class

<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 70 employees</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 100 employees</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 150 employees</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 250 employees</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 300 employees</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 80 employees</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 80 employees</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Consultant</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Politician</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Banker</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Banker</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Stockbroker</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Diplomat</p>		

Biographical context cards – Upper class

Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married

Biographical context cards – Upper class

Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent	Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family
Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family
Family background: Blended family		

Biographical context cards – Upper class

No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background

Biographical context cards – Upper class

No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	Immigrant background: Syria	Immigrant background: Syria
Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Turkey
Immigrant background: Turkey	Immigrant background: Turkey	Immigrant background: Belarus
Immigrant background: Poland		

Biographical context cards – Upper class

<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 3 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 3 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 3 family members, 5 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 5 family members, 7 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 5 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 4 family members, 5 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 3 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 4 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 4 family members, 6 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 4 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 4 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 5 family members, 7 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 4 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 5 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 5 family members, 7 rooms</p>

Biographical context cards – Upper class

<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 4 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 4 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 5 family members, 7 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 4 family members, 7 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 4 family members, 5 rooms</p>	

Biographical context cards – Upper class

<p>Special educational needs: Intellectual disability</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Intellectual disability</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Learning difficulties</p>
<p>Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Physical disability</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Physical disability</p>
<p>Special educational needs: Visual impairments</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Hearing impairments</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Hearing impairments</p>
<p>Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication</p>	<p>Special educational needs: none</p>	<p>Special educational needs: none</p>
<p>Special educational needs: none</p>	<p>Special educational needs: none</p>	<p>Special educational needs: none</p>

Biographical context cards – Upper class

Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none
Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none
Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none
Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none	Special educational needs: none
Special educational needs: none		

Biographical context cards – Middle class

Parents' occupation: Mason	Parents' occupation: Carpenter	Parents' occupation: Nursery school teacher
Parents' occupation: Nursery school teacher	Parents' occupation: Plumber	Parents' occupation: Teacher
Parents' occupation: Teacher	Parents' occupation: Secretary	Parents' occupation: Mechanic
Parents' occupation: Waiter	Parents' occupation: Insurance agent	Parents' occupation: Journalist
Parents' occupation: Tax accountant	Parents' occupation: Roadbuilder	Parents' occupation: Office clerk

Biographical context cards – Middle class

<p>Parents' occupation: Case worker</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Doctor's assitant</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Tax officer</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Florist</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Engineer</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Electrical engineer</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Scaffolder</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Salesperson</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Hairdresser</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 5 employees</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 5 employees</p>	<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 5 employees</p>
<p>Parents' occupation: Business owner, up to 5 employees</p>		

Biographical context cards – Middle class

Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family

Biographical context cards – Middle class

Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family
Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent		

Biographical context cards – Middle class

Immigrant background: Russia	Immigrant background: Russia	Immigrant background: Albania
Immigrant background: Albania	Immigrant background: Albania	Immigrant background: Turkey
Immigrant background: Turkey	Immigrant background: Poland	Immigrant background: Poland
Immigrant background: Serbia	Immigrant background: Serbia	Immigrant background: Afghanistan
Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Estonia

Biographical context cards – Middle class

Immigrant background: Syria	Immigrant background: Syria	Immigrant background: Syria
Immigrant background: Irak	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background		

Biographical context cards – Middle class

<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Terrace house 5 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Detached house 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Detached house 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Terrace house 4 family members, 5 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Terrace house 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 5 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Terrace house 4 family members, 5 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Terrace house 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Detached house 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Terrace house 3 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Terrace house 5 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Apartment 5 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Homeowner Terrace house 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>

Biographical context cards – Middle class

<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 3 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 3 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 4 rooms</p>		

Biographical context cards – Middle class

Special educational needs: Intellectual disability	Special educational needs: Intellectual disability	Special educational needs: Learning difficulties
Special educational needs: Learning difficulties	Special educational needs: Learning difficulties	Special educational needs: Physical disability
Special educational needs: Physical disability	Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs	Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs
Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication	Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication	Special educational needs: Visual impairments
Special educational needs: Hearing impairments	Special educational needs: Hearing impairments	Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication

Biographical context cards – Working class

Parents' occupation: Mason (unskilled)	Parents' occupation: Plumber (unskilled)	Parents' occupation: Checkout clerk
Parents' occupation: Hairdresser	Parents' occupation: Hairdresser	Parents' occupation: Cleaner
Parents' occupation: Cleaner	Parents' occupation: Seeking work	Parents' occupation: Seeking work
Parents' occupation: Seeking work	Parents' occupation: Seeking work	Parents' occupation: Seeking work
Parents' occupation: Seeking work	Parents' occupation: Seeking work	Parents' occupation: Seeking work

Biographical context cards – Working class

Parents' occupation: Seeking work	Parents' occupation: Seeking work	Parents' occupation: Seeking work
Parents' occupation: Construction assistant	Parents' occupation: Construction assistant	Parents' occupation: Waiter
Parents' occupation: Road builder	Parents' occupation: Salesperson	Parents' occupation: Kitchen helper
Parents' occupation: Housekeeper	Parents' occupation: Stockman / Stockwoman	Parents' occupation: Temporary employee
Parents' occupation: Temporary employee		

Biographical context cards – Working class

Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married	Family background: Parents are married
Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family
Family background: Blended family	Family background: Blended family	Family background: Single parent

Biographical context cards – Working class

Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent	Family background: Single parent
Family background: Single parent		

Biographical context cards – Working class

Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Afghanistan
Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Afghanistan	Immigrant background: Russia
Immigrant background: Russia	Immigrant background: Turkey	Immigrant background: Turkey
Immigrant background: Turkey	Immigrant background: Turkey	Immigrant background: Turkey
Immigrant background: Poland	Immigrant background: Poland	Immigrant background: Poland

Biographical context cards – Working class

Immigrant background: Poland	Immigrant background: Serbia	Immigrant background: Serbia
Immigrant background: Belarus	Immigrant background: Belarus	Immigrant background: Syria
Immigrant background: Syria	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background	No immigrant background	No immigrant background
No immigrant background		

Biographical context cards – Working class

<p>Living conditions: Tenant Terrace house 6 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Terrace house 6 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 6 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 6 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 3 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 7 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 7 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 3 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 2 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 2 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 3 rooms</p>

Biographical context cards – Working class

<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 3 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 7 family members, 5 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 7 family members, 6 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 3 family members, 2 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 3 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 3 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 4 family members, 3 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 5 family members, 4 rooms</p>	<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 7 family members, 5 rooms</p>
<p>Living conditions: Tenant Apartment 3 family members, 3 rooms</p>		

Biographical context cards – Working class

Special educational needs: Intellectual disability	Special educational needs: Intellectual disability	Special educational needs: Intellectual disability
Special educational needs: Learning difficulties	Special educational needs: Learning difficulties	Special educational needs: Learning difficulties
Special educational needs: Learning difficulties	Special educational needs: Learning difficulties	Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs
Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs	Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs	Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs
Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs	Special educational needs: Social and emotional mental health needs	Special educational needs: none

Biographical context cards – Middle class

<p>Special educational needs: none</p>	<p>Special educational needs: none</p>	<p>Special educational needs: none</p>
<p>Special educational needs: none</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication</p>
<p>Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Speech, language and communication</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Hearing impairments</p>
<p>Special educational needs: Visual impairments</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Physical disability</p>	<p>Special educational needs: Physical disability</p>
<p>Special educational needs: Physical disability</p>		

Personal event cards

Personal event

Forgot to do homework

You forgot to do your homework for English.

Depending on your class affiliation you lose:

- Upper class: - 5 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: - 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: - 15 pts cultural capital

Personal event

Illness

You're ill and cannot attend school.

Depending on your class affiliation you lose:

- Upper class: - 5 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: - 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: - 15 pts cultural capital

Personal event

Poetry

You memorized a poem and recited it in front of parents, teachers and students at a school event.

Depending on your class affiliation you gain:

- Upper class: + 5 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 15 pts cultural capital

Personal event

Forgot to do homework

You forgot to do your homework for Math.

Depending on your class affiliation you lose:

- Upper class: - 5 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: - 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: - 15 pts cultural capital

Personal event cards

Personal event

Natural science club

You spend a lot of time with the other members exploring the area and experimenting in nature. The others admire you and your work. Exchange 15 points of cultural capital for social capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 15 pts social capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts social capital
- Working class: + 5 pts social capital

Keep this card as long as you want to stay a member of the club (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to leave the club. Put the card back in the stack to leave the club.

Personal event

Additional homework

You successfully completed additional homework.

Depending on your class affiliation you gain:

- Upper class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 5 pts cultural capital

Personal event

Violin lessons

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 20 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 15 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to attend lessons (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit violin lessons. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons.

Personal event

Study sessions

You are very popular among your friends, and they enjoy studying with you. For your study sessions exchange 25 points of social capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 10 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to attend study sessions (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit your study sessions. Put the card back in the stack to quit sessions.

Personal event cards

Personal event

Study sessions

Ask a friend to study with you. Both of you must exchange 25 points of social capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 10 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you can find a study partner (i.e. someone else who wants to exchange capital). In each round, you must either find a study partner or put the card back in the stack.

Personal event

Drawing lessons

Exchange 20 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 5 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to attend lessons (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit drawing lessons. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons.

Personal event

Study sessions

You are very popular among your friends, and they enjoy studying with you. For your study sessions exchange 25 points of social capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 10 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to attend study sessions (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit your study sessions. Put the card back in the stack to quit sessions.

Personal event

Study sessions

Ask a friend to study with you. Both of you must exchange 25 points of social capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 10 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you can find a study partner (i.e. someone else who wants to exchange capital). In each round, you must either find a study partner or put the card back in the stack.

Personal event cards

Personal event

Take private tuition

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 5 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to take private tuition (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit private tuition. Put the card back in the stack to quit private tuition.

Personal event

Study sessions

Ask a friend to study with you. Both of you must exchange 25 points of social capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 10 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you can find a study partner (i.e. someone else who wants to exchange capital). In each round, you must either find a study partner or put the card back in the stack.

Personal event

Start a book club

Ask a friend to start a book club with you. Both of you must exchange 25 points of social capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 30 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 20 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you both want to stay in the book club (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit your book club. Put the card back in the stack as soon as one of you wants to quit.

Personal event

Join a sports club

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for social capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 15 pts social capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts social capital
- Working class: + 5 pts social capital

Keep this card as long as you want to stay in your club (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit the club. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons

Personal event cards

Personal event

Take foreign language lessons

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 30 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 20 pts cultural capital

If you have an immigrant background you receive an additional 5 pts of cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to continue with your lessons (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit lessons. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons.

Personal event

Join a band

You have to pay for your instrument and music lessons. Exchange 25 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 20 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 15 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to stay in the band (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit the band. Put the card back in the stack to quit the band.

Personal event

Exercise with friends

Your friends enjoy swimming, cycling and playing sports with you. Exchange 25 points of cultural capital for social capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 15 pts social capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts social capital
- Working class: + 5 pts social capital

Keep this card as long as you want to continue exercising with your friends (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to stop exercising. Put the card back in the stack to stop exercising.

Personal event

Join a sports club

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for social capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 15 pts social capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts social capital
- Working class: + 5 pts social capital

Keep this card as long as you want to stay in your club (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit the club. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons

Personal event cards

Personal event

Take piano lessons

Exchange 35 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 20 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 15 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to take piano lessons (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit lessons. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons.

Personal event

Take breakdance lessons

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for social capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 5 pts social capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts social capital
- Working class: + 15 pts social capital

Keep this card as long as you want to take breakdance lessons (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit lessons. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons.

Personal event

Conflict resolution

Your teacher has chosen you as conflict moderator for the class. You receive 20 points of social capital regardless of your class affiliation:

Personal event

Cultural events with your parents

Your parents take you to the museum on a regular basis. You also attend plays and classical concerts together.

Depending on your class affiliation you receive:

- Upper class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 5 pts cultural capital

Personal event cards

Personal event

Injury during P.E.

You hurt yourself during P.E.:

You can't walk for the next three rounds. For these rounds you are considered physically disabled.

That means that you can't receive any capital through sports activities.

Put this card back on the stack after three rounds.

Personal event

Your phone breaks

Middle class or working class players can't afford a new phone. They'll have to get by without it:

You lose 10 points of social capital and 10 points of cultural capital each round from now on or until you get a new phone.

Upper class players get a new phone right away:

You lose 10 points of social capital and cultural capital once.

Personal event

Quit the sports club

Your parents discontinue your membership. Put your membership card back in the stack.

Put this card back and draw a new card if you're currently not a member of a sports club.

Personal event

You are elected class representative

You receive 20 points of social capital regardless of class affiliation.

Personal event cards

Personal event

Buy a horse

You have the opportunity to buy a horse. You can choose to exchange 100 points of economic capital for social capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts social capital
- Middle class: + 20 pts social capital
- Working class: + 15 pts social capital

If you also take riding lessons you can exchange 50 points of economic capital for social capital at the above exchange rates. You can keep this card as long as you want to take riding lessons (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit lessons. Put the card back in the stack to quit lessons.

Personal event

You win a sports tournament with your club

You receive 15 points of social capital and 10 points of cultural capital regardless of class affiliation.

Put this card back and draw a new card if you're currently not a member of a sports club.

Personal event

Buy prestigious items (brand-name clothing etc.)

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for social capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 20 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 15 pts cultural capital

Personal event

Your parents give you a new phone

You immediately receive 15 points of social capital and 20 points of cultural capital regardless of class affiliation.

In each of the following rounds you will receive 5 points of social capital and 5 points of cultural capital. But you also lose 5 points of economic capital paying for your phone contract.

You can keep this card as long as you want to pay for your phone contract (i.e. exchange capital) or until your phone breaks. In each round, you must either pay your phone contract or get rid of your phone. Put the card back in the stack to get rid of your phone.

Personal event cards

Personal event

Go on holiday with your parents

If you have an immigrant background, you'll visit family in your parents' country. You receive 10 points of cultural capital and 10 points of social capital.

All other players receive 15 points of cultural capital and 15 points of social capital.

Personal event

Your parents get a divorce

You move in with one of your parents (change biographical background) and lose 30 points of social capital.

This affects your capital distribution after each round. Depending on class affiliation you must deduct:

- Upper class: -5 pts economic capital
- Middle class: -10 pts economic capital
- Working class: -15 pts economic capital

Keep this card for the rest of the game.

Put this card back and draw a new card if your parents are already divorced.

Personal event

Your parents inherit money

In this round and the next you receive:

- Upper class: + 25 pts economic capital
- Middle class: + 15 pts economic capital
- Working class: + 5 pts economic capital

Personal event

Start a book club

Ask a friend to start a book club with you. Both of you must exchange 25 points of social capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

- Upper class: + 30 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 25 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 20 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you both want to stay in the book club (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit your book club. Put the card back in the stack as soon as one of you wants to quit.

Personal event cards

Personal event

You lose a loved one

You lose 15 points of social capital.

You have to skip the next round and won't receive any capital.

Personal event

Take private tuition

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

-
- Upper class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 5 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to take private tuition (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit private tuition. Put the card back in the stack to quit private tuition.

Personal event

Babysit your siblings

You lose 15 points of cultural capital.

You have to skip the next round and won't receive any capital.

Personal event

Take private tuition

Exchange 25 points of economic capital for cultural capital at the following exchange rate:

-
- Upper class: + 15 pts cultural capital
- Middle class: + 10 pts cultural capital
- Working class: + 5 pts cultural capital

Keep this card as long as you want to take private tuition (i.e. exchange capital). In each round, you must either exchange capital or decide to quit private tuition. Put the card back in the stack to quit private tuition.

Personal event cards

Personal event

Both parents work full-time
or
Single parent works two jobs

This affects your capital distribution after each round. Depending on class affiliation you must add/deduct:

- Upper class: +35 pts economic capital
+5 pts social capital
- Middle class: +25 pts economic capital
-10 pts social capital
- Working class: +15 pts economic capital
- -15 pts social capital

Keep this card as long as your parents' work situation stays the same.

Personal event

One of your parents loses their job

You have to skip the next round and won't receive any capital.

Put this card back and draw a new card if your parents were already unemployed.

General event cards

General event

Adventure trip

A local club has organized an adventure trip for disadvantaged kids. It is free for all **working class players**.

Players with **special educational needs** can't go.

Everyone else must roll a die: If they roll a 2 or above they can come on the trip as helpers.

All **working class participants** receive 15 points of social capital and 15 points of cultural capital.

All **helpers** receive 10 points of social capital and 10 points of cultural capital.

General event

Exam in English

There will be an English exam at the end of the next round.

All players with **at least 50 points of cultural capital** and no immigrant background pass the exam and receive 20 points of cultural capital.

All players with **at least 50 points of cultural capital and an immigrant background** pass the exam but do not receive any additional capital.

All players with **less than 50 points of cultural capital** fail the exam and lose 20 points of cultural capital.

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General event

Exam in Math

There will be a Math exam at the end of the next round.

All **male players** with at least 30 points of cultural capital pass the exam and receive 10 points of cultural capital.

All **male players** with less than 30 points of cultural capital fail the exam and lose 10 points of cultural capital.

Female players need 40 points of cultural capital to pass the exam. They receive 5 points of cultural capital if they pass and lose 15 points of cultural capital if they fail.

General event

Dictation exercise

There will be a dictation exercise at the end of the next round.

All players with **at least 40 points of cultural capital** will pass and receive 15 points of cultural capital.

All players with **less than 40 points of cultural capital** will fail and lose 15 points of cultural capital.

Players with an **immigrant background** need 50 points of cultural capital to pass. They receive 10 points of cultural capital if they pass and lose 20 points of cultural capital if they fail.

General event cards

General event

Economic crisis

Due to a prolonged economic crisis, wages are falling and welfare programs are cut back. All families have less money at their disposal

Depending on class affiliation you lose:

Upper class: -15 pts economic capital, -10 pts cultural capital, -5 pts social capital

Middle class: -20 pts economic capital, -15 pts cultural capital, -10 pts social capital

Working class: -25 pts economic capital, -10 pts cultural capital, -15 pts social capital

General event

School development project: Diversity and Inclusion

Your school participates in a school development project and takes important steps towards becoming more inclusive. All students at the school benefit from these developments.

All players receive 20 points of social capital and 20 points of cultural capital.

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General event

Inclusive didactics

Your teacher is interested in inclusive didactics. In their teaching, they take into account a diversity of learning levels and different learning needs.

All players with **special educational needs, immigrant background and/or working class** affiliation receive 25 points of social capital and 25 points of cultural capital.

Everyone else receives 20 points of social capital and 20 points of cultural capital.

General event

Lack of cooperation among teachers

Your teachers disagree on the students' learning levels and their progress. They no longer cooperate in planning your lessons. This negatively affects the quality of your lessons.

All players with **special educational needs, immigrant background and/or working class** affiliation lose 10 points of cultural capital.

Everyone else loses 5 points of social capital and 10 points of cultural capital.

General event cards

General event

Absent teacher

Your English teacher is absent for an indefinite period of time due to long-term illness. The school cannot find a suitable replacement. The changing substitute teachers cannot maintain a coherent lesson plan.

All players with **special educational needs, immigrant background and/or working class** affiliation lose 10 points of social capital and 15 points of cultural capital.

Everyone else loses 5 points of social capital and 10 points of cultural capital.

General event

Change of government: Cuts in education

Due to the new government's severe cuts in education teachers are being let go and classes are getting bigger.

All players with **special educational needs, immigrant background and/or working class** affiliation lose 10 points of social capital and 15 points of cultural capital.

Everyone else loses 5 points of social capital and 10 points of cultural capital.

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General event

Circus project

A local club has organized a circus project that will take place at your school. The project ends with a big performance in the assembly hall. It is free for **working class players**.

Everyone else must roll a die: If they roll a 2 or above they can attend the performance.

All **working class** players participating in the project receive 15 points of social capital and 15 points of cultural capital.

Everyone attending the performance receives 10 points of social capital and 10 points of cultural capital.

General event

Sports day at school

Your school is organizing a sports day with various track and field activities. Students compete against each other in different disciplines.

Players with **physical disabilities** cannot participate and won't receive any capital.

All participating players, who are currently **members of a sports club**, receive 10 points of social capital and 15 points of cultural capital.

All participating players, who are **not members of a sports club**, receive 5 points of social capital and 15 points of cultural capital.

General event cards

General event

A week of hiking field trips

This week the whole school is going hiking in the area. Each day you explore a new trail nearby.

Players with **physical disabilities** cannot participate and won't receive any capital.

Everyone else receives 10 points of social capital and 15 points of cultural capital.

General event

Grammar exam in English

There will be an English grammar exam at the end of the next round.

All players with **at least 30 points of cultural capital** will pass and receive 10 points of cultural capital.

All players with **less than 30 points of cultural capital** will fail and lose 10 points of cultural capital.

Players with an **immigrant background** need 40 points of cultural capital to pass. They receive 5 points of cultural capital if they pass and lose 15 points of cultural capital if they fail

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General event

General knowledge exam

There will be a general knowledge exam at the end of the next round.

All players with **at least 60 points of cultural capital** will pass and receive 30 points of cultural capital.

All players with **less than 60 points of cultural capital** will fail and lose 30 points of cultural capital.

Players with **special educational needs** need 70 points of cultural capital to pass. They receive 25 points of cultural capital if they pass and lose 35 points of cultural capital if they fail

